

ARE ZOOS DOING MORE HARM THAN GOOD TO THE ENVIRONMENT?**Kamoldinova Xulkaroy Abduvahob qizi**

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Ilmiy rahbar:

<https://doi.org/>**Аннотация.**

В данной статье рассматривается влияние зоопарков на охрану окружающей среды и благополучие животных. Особое внимание уделяется как положительным, так и отрицательным аспектам содержания животных в неволе. Анализируются современные подходы к сохранению исчезающих видов, а также проблемы, связанные с условиями содержания животных в зоопарках.

Ключевые слова: зоопарки, охрана окружающей среды, благополучие животных, исчезающие виды, биоразнообразие.

Annotation.

This article examines the impact of zoos on environmental conservation and animal well-being. Special attention is given to both the positive and negative aspects of keeping animals in captivity. The study analyzes modern approaches to protecting endangered species as well as challenges related to animal living conditions in zoos.

Keywords: zoos, environmental conservation, animal welfare, endangered species, biodiversity.

Annotatsiya.

Mazkur maqolada hayvonot bog'larining atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish va hayvonlar farovonligiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Asosan hayvonlarni asirlikda saqlashning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, yo'qolib borayotgan turlarni saqlash usullari va hayvonlar yashash sharoitlari bilan bog'liq muammolar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: hayvonot bog'lari, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, hayvonlar farovonligi, yo'qolib borayotgan turlar, bioxilma-xillik.

Introduction

In recent years, Zoos plays an important role in modern society and it has become a main topic for active debate. Many years ago, zoos were created to display animals for entertainment, but today they are considered organisations for education and conservation.

Nowadays, people pay more attention to save the environment. In this case, animal rights have become a crucial part in society too. Some researchers argue that zoos are beneficial, while others think that they are harmful for animals.

The research question of this study is: How do zoos impact wildlife conservation efforts and the overall well-being of animals? The main purpose of this article is to analyze both the positive and negative sides of zoos and assess their role in the modern world.

Methods of Research

Different kinds of methods were used to learn the aim of this research. First, scientific articles and online sources related to zoos were explored and these sources helped to identify the main part of the problem. Therefore, traditional and modern zoos are compared and their differences were studied. The experiences of various zoos were reviewed and which one worked better was analyzed. As part of the study, the life of animals in captivity and their life in the wild were compared. This approach allowed for a broader understanding of the topic.

Results of the Research

The results show that zoos have both advantages and disadvantages on the environment and animals. One of the main advantages of zoos is that many zoos breed endangered animals. This helps to increase the number of animals. In some cases, the animals are released back into the wild. Zoos play a crucial role in educating people, especially students, they learn about animals, ecosystems and the importance of nature conservation. This improves environmental awareness of nature conservation. However, there are some significant disadvantages of zoos. We see, animals live in small places and they are often kept in small cages, these conditions do not correspond to their natural environment. This can establish the stress, abnormal behaviour, and some serious health problems on animals.

Discussion

The results show that, the effect of zoos depends on their purpose and management. Modern zoos try to protect animals. They create better living conditions and a safe environment for endangered animals and contribute to scientific research. Meanwhile, traditional zoos that mostly focus on entertainment can be harmful. Keeping animals in captivity for long periods of time negatively affects their natural instincts and behaviours. Another important issue is the ethical aspect. Many people believe that animals should live freely not in cages. This raises questions about the moral responsibility of humans toward animals.

Prospects of Research

Near the future, the professors would opt for another option to zoos. We can take samples of nature reserves or virtual education methods. These methods can lead to reduction in animals in capacity. Moreover, we need to study the effect of long-term capacity on animals. Life can be improved by them. Good conditions are enhanced with the modern technology for the animals.

Conclusion

In conclusion, zoos have both positive and negative impacts on the environment and animal welfare. While, they play an important role in protecting animals, saving endangered species and educating people, they can also harm animals if mismanagement. Therefore, zoos must continue to develop and focus on conservation, education and improving animal welfare. Only then, they can truly play a positive role in protecting the environment.

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